

THE ROLE OF APPLYING TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE: A FIELD STUDY IN YEMENI BANKS

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the role of applying total quality management in Yemeni banks and its dimensions in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks. The study was targeted through a comprehensive survey of all employees, including banking and administrative leaders, in Yemeni banks. The total study population reached (758) leaders, and (678) were analyzed. The study relied on the descriptive analytical approach. The study relied on the questionnaire as the main tool for all data, and the data was analyzed using The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) the most important conclusions were: There is a positive role in applying total quality management in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks, and the continuous improvement dimension was the most influential, while the teamwork dimension was the least influential in institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Keywords: Total Quality Management, Improving Institutional Performance, Yemeni Banks.

INTRODUCTION

After the year 1980, the concept of total quality management began to emerge strongly, due to the intensity of global competition that emerged with the Japanese industry sweeping the global market, and after European and American companies lost their position in the global market, which prompted American companies to modify the concept of total quality management by launching the concept of quality management. The strategy (Al-Shuqairat, 2022, p. 70).

Interest in applying the total quality management approach has emerged as a description of an organization's culture, position, and organization and as a distinct management method in organizations as a result of the tremendous success it has achieved in various service, industrial, and economic institutions in many countries, which strive to provide customers with services that meet their needs. Total Quality Management is also considered a common management approach developed by American industry during and before World War II.

Although it began in the United States, it was developed and refined by Japanese industry (Altahayneh, 2014, P. 109-114). Performance improvement is an approach to determining how organizations achieve their goals, and should include all levels within the organization with an orientation toward continuous improvement of its goals. The administrative development process requires evaluating the performance of employees, which provides important information about their level of performance reveals the latent energies and capabilities of individuals and is considered an entry point for redistribution. Responsibilities, burdens and roles to ensure the benefit of these untapped human energies and capabilities (Al-Mubaideen, 2013, p. 689).

The total quality management system is closely linked to institutional performance, as it is a gateway to continuous improvement in the organization's operations. Applying the total quality management approach through continuous improvement of processes, monitoring the quality of performance, research and development, and empowering and participating employees reflects significantly and positively on the overall outstanding performance of the organization (Abdu Rahman, 2018, p. 92).

Many studies focused on total quality management in improving institutional performance. A study (Al-Shami, 2020) To learn about the application of total quality management and its relationship to the level of performance in Yemeni private schools. It has reached results, the most important of which is that there is a statistically significant role for applying total quality management in improving institutional performance in Yemeni private schools. And study (Abdullah and Muhammadin, 2022) To identify the impact of comprehensive quality management on the financial performance of Sudanese banks. It reached results, the most important of which is the presence of an impact of comprehensive quality management on the financial performance of Sudanese banks.

A study (Alkhitan, 2022). To identify the impact of business strategy on institutional performance through total quality management, an applied study on food industry companies in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

The study showed the impact of the dimensions of comprehensive quality on the institutional performance of Jordanian food factories. And study (Shahid, et al, 2014). To identify the relationship between the dimensions of total quality management and institutional performance in Pakistan.

The results show that there is a strong positive relationship between the dimensions of total quality management and institutional performance in Pakistan. A study (Naeem, 2008) To learn about the recommended total quality management for the Pakistani banking sector.

The results indicate that one-fifth of the banks operating in Pakistan have fully comprehensive quality management. And study (Adedira, 2008) To learn about testing the impact of total quality management on the performance and satisfaction of stakeholders (shareholders), reached results, the most important of which is that there is an impact of total quality management on performance and stakeholder satisfaction.

Based on the above, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the concept of total quality management in improving institutional performance, in a manner appropriate to the stage and achieving the desired objectives of the study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A: Total Quality Management

Banks rely on applying advanced methods of total quality management, which are primarily concerned with increasing customer satisfaction through an integrated framework that studies the relationships between various elements at the institution level and makes data-based decisions to reduce errors and waste in operations. Improving the quality of banking services is linked to expanding the scope of banks' work and ease of access to them, diversifying the services provided to customers, ensuring banking service, ensuring the application of quality to all services, and introducing information and communications technologies (Gibran and Odeh, 2022, p.

108). The concept of total quality management is considered one of the modern management concepts that aim to continuously improve and develop performance by responding to customer requirements (Abed, 2017, P. 7). Total Quality Management is also defined as a process of continuous improvement of quality, through developing and maintaining the organization's capabilities, achieving customer desires, and working to find and apply them in any aspect of work, by knowing the customer's needs, then find out how satisfied he is with the services provided to him (Al-Awadi, 2018, P. 7).

The importance of comprehensive quality comes from the keenness of business organizations to provide services with characteristics and characteristics that are distinct from their counterparts from other institutions in the environment in which they exist. This may push the ambition of business organizations to excel on an international scale, which is a legitimate goal, but it needs components.

Comprehensive quality lies in the fact that the institution provides the service to achieve the goals of the customer who seeks to obtain the best performance and thus gain his satisfaction and acceptance of the service. As a result of the demand for the service, leads to an expansion of the institution's market share as the number of customers increases (Abu Hilweh, 2018, P.35). There is no agreement between scholars and researchers on the number of original principles of total quality management. Some of them said that there are 5 principles, some of them said 10 principles and some of them said 15.

According to the points of view, many researchers reach their conclusions. The basic principles of total quality management are top leadership commitment, customer focus, continuous improvement and teamwork (Mohyaldeen, 2023, p. 236). The first principle is the commitment of senior management: Senior management must implement comprehensive quality management and be committed to it, and the process of change should be a priority. Some employees resist change, and senior management must contribute to implementing and achieving quality.

Commitment is to support senior management in institutions for the quality process and work on it (Al-Saqour, 2022, P. 59). Senior management must study all procedures and processes to solve the problems facing the application of quality management. It is necessary to note that the commitment of senior management to the application of total quality management is reflected within the organization's mission and goals (Thawabith, 2016, P. 40).

The second principle is customer focus, the criterion of success for any institution, and the first goal is the satisfaction of the beneficiary or customer with the services provided to him. This principle focuses on knowing the needs and expectations of the customer to include them in the design of the services provided to customers (Al-Damen, 2017, P. 192).

Focusing on the customer is considered one of the most important principles of all because it contributes to strengthening the relationship between the organization and its current and potential customers. It increases management's understanding of their needs and desires, to provide what is expected in the best way (Dissanayake, 2014, P. 293).

The third principle: Continuous improvement is the constant desire of an organization to achieve gradual and fundamental improvement in all activities and services. Perhaps the method of benchmarking is the most widely used method for continuous improvement and development.

The formulation of performance improvement is part of the philosophy of quality management. Overall, senior management must show what expresses its approach, and this philosophy was transferred to the organization to meet it in all its internal operations because of its impact on its development and contribution to its success (Sanaa, 2020, P. 59).

The fourth principle is teamwork. It means breaking down the traditional barriers of different levels of organization between executives and consultants. Rather, work groups must be formed that bear joint responsibility for the comprehensive quality of services provided and focus on involving all employees, granting powers to employees, providing amenities, and employee commitment (Al-amari, 2011, p. 201).

B: Institutional Performance

The origin of the word or term “performance” is Latin, but it is the English language that gave it a clear and specific meaning, “to perform,” meaning to perform a job, accomplish an activity, or carry out a task, or to perform an action that helps reach the set goals (Zahra, 2011, p. 201). The concept of performance in general also refers to that action that leads to the completion of work as it should be done, and which is characterized by comprehensiveness and continuity. Therefore, this meaning is the determinant of the success and survival of the institution, and in its target markets. It also reflects at the same time the extent of the institution’s ability to adapt to environment or its failure to achieve the required adaptation. (Al-Zahrani, 2014, p. 30). The current study adopted the elements of the balanced scorecard model in terms of the dimensions of measuring organizational performance, as it provides a balanced view of the factors important for the success of organizations.

The balanced scorecard model is characterized by the fact that it contributes to achieving social responsibility, community service, environmental protection, and increasing employee skills and work effectiveness in banks (Thabet, 2023, p. 18). It can be measured from the perspective of the financial dimension. It is the first dimension of the scorecard in banking institutions, Islamic and commercial banks, and it includes several strategic criteria, such as achieving fair profit and not achieving maximum profit. It is an achievable strategic goal, and one of the basic criteria that must be met is the balanced growth standard for a mix of revenues. of investment activities, and reduce costs to the maximum possible extent, to achieve the maximum possible effectiveness.

This dimension also contains purely financial objectives such as return on investment, cost of products, profitability, cash flow, and at some point, such as cash flow in times of hardship. (Atkinson et al, 2012, p50). The second dimension, customers, is defined as the bank’s ability to meet customers’ requirements and needs by providing goods and services of high value and quality that gain their satisfaction and meet their ambitions and desires. The modern management philosophy shows more care to satisfy customers, and low performance in this perspective is a major indicator of the coming decline, even if the picture appears The current finances are good, and this dimension is measured by market share, returns according to the procedure, customer satisfaction rate, and their loyalty rate (Brish and Yahyaoui, 2012, p. 38). The third

dimension is operations, which means collecting the internal processes, activities, and events that distinguish the organization from other business organizations, and through which the desires of customers and owners are met.

This dimension searches for how to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of basic operations that achieve strategic objectives and allow for the provision of services that attract customers and ensure returns to shareholders, by presenting sources of strength and weakness in the internal and basic operations of the organization, rationalizing costs, and identifying pivotal operations and the extent of their ability to meet customer requirements (Sayeh, 2021, p. 124).

The fourth dimension is learning and growth, which is defined as the bank's ability to develop the capabilities of employees and encourage innovation systems within the bank, as they are its infrastructure that works to build and develop the institution in the long term. Institutions that focus on the perspective of learning and growth need correct systems for employees to facilitate the process of supporting them to achieve goals.

Without Learning and Growth: Being unable to adapt to the dynamic environment, to achieve successful adaptation they must continue to train their workers on modern technologies. And on information systems to facilitate meeting customers' renewed requirements (Talib and Hamid, 2018).

Figure 1: Research model of the study

Hypotheses:

Main Hypothesis: There is a statistically significant role for total quality management in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

From this main hypothesis, the following sub-hypotheses branch out:

Sub-Hypothesis 1: There is a statistically significant role for senior management commitment in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Sub-Hypothesis 2: There is a statistically significant role for the Focus on the customer in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Sub-Hypothesis 3: There is a statistically significant role for Employee participation in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Sub-Hypothesis 4: There is a statistically significant role for Continuous improvement in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

METHOD

The study population consists of the main centers of Yemeni banks in the capital, Sana'a, numbering (13 banks), where the questionnaire was used for field study procedures, for several (10 banks), and 3 banks were excluded because they apologized for not dealing with any questionnaires from university students, and it was a sample The target population (758 individuals) consists of all employees in senior administrative and supervisory positions with long service and experience. The descriptive analytical approach was used, and the statistical package program (SPSS) was used to analyze the data.

First: Total Quality Management.

Table (1): Means Averages and standard deviations of the sample members' estimates of the level of implementation of comprehensive quality management in Yemeni banks.

Dimension	Mean Average	Standard deviation	Relative Weight	Linguistic Significance
Senior management commitment	4.76	1.46	68.00	High
Focus on the customer	4.80	1.60	68.57%	High
Continuous improvement	4.85	1.49	69.29%	High
teamwork	4.65	1.52	66.43%	High
Total Quality Management	4.76	1.12	68.00%	High

It was shown in Table (1) that the highest application of total quality management in Yemeni banks was represented by the continuous improvement dimension, as it obtained an arithmetic mean of (4.85) with a standard deviation of (1.49) and a percentage of (69.29%) at a high level.

The focus dimension came in second place. On clients, it obtained an arithmetic mean of (4.80) with a standard deviation of (1.60) and a percentage of (68.57%) at a high level.

As for the third place, it received the dimension of senior management's commitments, where it obtained an arithmetic mean of (4.76) with a standard deviation of (1.46) and a ratio of (68.00%). At a high level, the teamwork dimension ranked fourth and last. obtained an arithmetic mean of (4.65) with a standard deviation of (66.43%) and a high level.

The results also showed in general that the level of application of total quality management in Yemeni banks is high, as it obtained an arithmetic mean of (4.76) and a standard deviation of (1.41) with a percentage of (68.00%). The researchers attribute this to the extent of Yemeni banks' interest in applying total quality management and its importance in the banking sector Yemeni.

Second: Improving institutional performance

Table (2): Means Averages and standard deviations of the average responses of study sample members about the level of institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Dimension	Mean Average	Standard deviation	Relative weight	Linguistic Significance
Financial	4.75	1.45	67.86%	High
Customer	4.72	1.52	67.43%	High
Internal processes	4.69	1.50	67.00%	High
Learning and growth	4.51	1.61	64.43%	Middle
Improving bank performance	4.67	1.44	66.71%	High

Table (2) shows the following: The highest institutional performance in Yemeni banks was represented by the financial dimension, where it obtained an arithmetic mean of (4.75) and a standard deviation of (1.45) with a rate of (67.86%) at a high level.

The customer dimension came in second place, where it obtained An arithmetic average of (4.72) with a standard deviation of (1.52) at a rate of (67.43%) and at a high level.

In third place came the operations dimension, where it obtained an arithmetic average of (4.69) with a standard deviation of (1.50) at a rate of (67.00%) at a high level, while the dimension of learning and growth came. In the fourth and final order, it obtained an arithmetic mean of (4.51) with a standard deviation of (1.61) and a percentage of (64.43%), which represents an average level.

The results also showed in general that the level of institutional performance in Yemeni banks is high, with an arithmetic mean of (4.67) and a standard deviation of (1.44) with a percentage of (66.71%). The researchers attribute this to the interest of Yemeni banks in improving their institutional performance.

Hypothesis testing

First: the main hypothesis

There is a statistically significant role for applying total quality management in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

The key hypothesis (effect of total quality management in improving institutional performance) was examined using simple linear regression, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Model estimation between strategic leadership and total quality management

Independent variable	Path	Dependent variable	R ²	Beta	T	P-Value
Total quality management	-->	improving institutional performance	0.784	0.906	49.560	0.000

Through the previous table (3), the results of simple linear regression showed the existence of a statistically significant relationship to the role of the independent variable (application of comprehensive quality management) on the dependent variable (institutional performance), where the level of significance was (0.000), as indicated by the results of the coefficient of determination, the value of which was ($R^2 = 0.784$), meaning that (78.4%) of the changes (variance) occurring in institutional performance are mainly due to the independent variable applying comprehensive quality, while (21.6%) of the remainder of the variance in the changes that occur in institutional performance in Yemeni banks is due to variables Other, the degree of influence reached ($Beta = 0.906$), which means that improving the level of practice of applying total quality management by one degree results in an improvement in institutional performance in Yemeni banks by (90.6%), as well as the calculated T value of (49.560) with a level of significance. (0.000) It is less than the level of moral significance (0.05).

From the above, through the coefficient of determination (R^2), the influence factor (Beta), the value of (T), and the level of statistical significance, and based on the above, we conclude that the main hypothesis is correct, so it is accepted, which It states that: There is a statistically significant role for applying total quality management in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks, and the level of that role is significant.

Second: Testing the sub-hypotheses.

Testing the sub-hypotheses was performed as follows:

Sub-Hypothesis 1: There is a statistically significant role for senior management commitment in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Sub-Hypothesis 2: There is a statistically significant role for the Focus on the customer in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Sub-Hypothesis 3: There is a statistically significant role for Employee participation in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Sub-Hypothesis 4: There is a statistically significant role for Continuous improvement in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

Role of total quality management in improving institutional performance was examined using multiple linear regression, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Model estimation between independent variables and improving institutional performance

Independent variable	Path	Dependent variable	Beta	T	P-Value
Senior management commitment	-->	improving institutional performance	0.184	5.303	0.000
Focus on the customer	-->	improving institutional performance	0.060	2.050	0.041
Continuous improvement	-->	improving institutional performance	0.147	3.562	0.000
Teamwork	-->	improving institutional performance	0.528	17.269	0.000

It was shown from the previous table that there is a statistically significant role for the interaction of all dimensions of the independent variable (top management commitment, customer focus, continuous improvement, teamwork) in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks, as the results showed that the value of the beta effect rate (Beta) was (0.184, 0.060, 0.147, 0.528) respectively and at a significance level (0.000, 0.041, 0.000, 0.000) in all dimensions, which is less than the moral significance level (0.05).

This result indicates that assuming the effect of any other variables is neutralized, there will be an increase in the level of improvement (Top management commitment, customer focus, continuous improvement, teamwork). One degree leads to an increase of (90.5%) in improving the overall institutional performance of Yemeni banks. It was found that the teamwork dimension is considered the most influential dimension in improving institutional performance, followed by the dimension of supporting senior management's commitment, and then the continuous improvement dimension, then the customer focus dimension. Hence accepting all sub-hypotheses.

CONCLUSIONS

There is great interest in applying total quality management in Yemeni banks in general in all its dimensions, which means that bank departments are interested in the importance of applying total quality to provide high-quality banking services.

After continuous improvement, the highest dimensions of comprehensive quality management were applied in Yemeni banks, which means that the banks were interested in continuous improvement and development, and the least application was after teamwork.

There is a varying positive role for the dimensions of total quality management in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

There is great interest and a high level in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks.

The highest application of the dimensions of total quality management is the financial dimension, and the lowest is the institutional performance dimension of learning and growth, at an average level.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Continuing to apply total quality management more effectively in all its dimensions until it leads to improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks (study sample).

Increased interest in improving institutional performance in Yemeni banks for the banks' survival and continuity.

Yemeni banks (study sample) should pay more attention to customer satisfaction and meet their needs on an ongoing basis to meet their desires.

Banks' interest in keeping up to date with recent developments and banking developments leads them to improve the banking services they provide.

Yemeni banks (study sample) should work according to one team and collective work to achieve a more comprehensive quality management application.

It is necessary to give employees in Yemeni banks (study sample) active participation in decision-making to ensure their acceptance of decisions and create mutual trust between them and the bank management.

The necessity of establishing an electronic library in Yemeni banks (study sample) that helps employees with continuous education and keeping pace with banking developments.

The researchers recommend intensifying the training programs received by employees in Yemeni banks (study sample) in a more effective way, through which qualified leaders emerge, which facilitates the application of total quality management, and through qualitative training, institutional performance is improved.

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